

Assessing the potential risks of flooding in Ca Mau province in the context of climate change and sea level rise

*Ngo Thi Hai Yen

Hanoi National University of Education, Vietnam
136 Xuan Thuy Street, Cau Giay District, Hanoi, Vietnam

*Corresponding author: **Ngo Thi Hai Yen**

Hanoi National University of Education, Vietnam
136 Xuan Thuy Street, Cau Giay District, Hanoi, Vietnam

Abstract

Climate change and sea level rise are increasingly becoming major concerns for coastal communities worldwide, including Vietnam. Ca Mau Province, located in the southwestern part of Vietnam, is particularly vulnerable to flooding due to its low-lying coastal area. Rising sea levels and more frequent extreme weather events, such as heavy rainfall events, threaten to exacerbate flooding in the region. In recent years, Ca Mau Province has experienced several devastating flooding events, resulting in significant economic losses, displacement of people, and damage to infrastructure and agriculture.

This study aims to assess the potential risks of flooding in Ca Mau Province in the context of climate change and sea level rise. Using a combination of historical rainfall data, the study will identify the most vulnerable areas and communities in Ca Mau Province and estimate the potential impacts of flooding on the infrastructure, and population. The study will also examine the effectiveness of current flood risk management strategies and identify areas for improvement. The findings will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the flood risks in Ca Mau Province and decision-making, ultimately contributing to the development of more effective flood risk management strategies and reducing the vulnerability of communities to flooding.

Keywords: Climate variability, sea level rise, hydraulic projects, flooding, risk management.

1. Introduction

Climate change is a pressing global issue that affects various countries around the world, including Vietnam [1, 2]. Increasing urbanization process combined with climate change has resulted in the increased risk of flooding in the low-lying coastal urban areas (LCU) [3, 4]. Human activities contribute to increase the flood risks in the LCU due to local changes in increasing proportion of impervious surfaces, combined with the attenuation of river networks and inadequate drainage facilities, has increased the risk of torrential rain in urban areas around the world [5, 6]. These have led to profound transformations in the types of land used in urban areas, resulting in a distinct underlying surface characteristic that diverges from the natural landscape [7, 8]. Specifically, the proportion of impervious surfaces has risen substantially, while the density of river networks has been significantly diminished [15, 17]. According to Carter and Jackson (2007), urbanization in the LCU leads to the replacement of vegetation, which plays a crucial role in intercepting and storing rainfall, thereby altering the characteristics of surface runoff [18, 19]. In addition, climate change is expected to increase extreme weather events such as droughts, heat waves, and heavy rainfall events [9, 10, 14]. IPCC (2014) reported that the frequency and severity of flooding in the LCU are exacerbated by heavy rainfall events under the negative impacts of climate change. Thus, assessing the effect of future climate change on urban flooding and adopting effective flood management measures is becoming increasingly important [11, 12, 13].

Ca Mau province is located in the southwestern part of the Mekong Delta, is particularly vulnerable to climate change due to its LCU. The region is prone to frequent and severe flooding, which has significant impacts on the economy, society, human safety and property. The increasing frequency and intensity of heavy rainfall events, combined with rising

sea levels, have exacerbated the flooding risk in Ca Mau in recent years [7, 16]. For instance, on October 19, 2020, a high tide combined with prolonged heavy rainfall flooded over 16,000 hectares of rice cultivation paddies in Tran Van Thoi district of Ca Mau province. The most recent event occurring on October 2, 2023, which caused localized flooding on many roads and some low-lying areas of more than 349 houses, affecting people's lives and production (Source: Communist Party of Vietnam Electronic News).

This study aims to assess the potential risks of flooding in Ca Mau province in the context of climate change and sea level rise. The study is situated in the context of urbanization and climate change, which have been identified as major drivers of flooding in LCU. The study will examine the impacts of climate change on extreme rainfall events and urban flooding.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Description of the study area

Ca Mau province, the southernmost province of Vietnam, is situated in the Mekong Delta, a low-lying coast region prone to frequent flooding [7, 8]. The province is bordered by the East Sea to the east, the Gulf of Thailand to the west and south, and the provinces of Bac Lieu and Kien Giang to the north [7, 20]. With a total area of 5331 km², Ca Mau province is a vast and flat coastal plain, featuring a dense network of natural channels and a coastline of approximately 254 km [7, 19]. Rainfall has a strong variation in seasonal and intensity. Southwest monsoon is the main source of rainfall during wet season, and its intensity increases from May to October, and its peak commonly occurs in October (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Map of the study area

The province's elevation is extremely low, with an average height of just 0.5 meters above sea level, making it one of the most vulnerable areas to flooding in Vietnam [7, 19]. Ca Mau province experiences a tropical monsoon climate, characterized by high temperatures and distinct wet and dry seasons. The rainy season, which lasts from May to November, brings heavy rainfall and frequent flooding, while the dry season, from December to April, is marked by a significant reduction in rainfall. The province receives an average of 165 rainy days per year, with an annual rainfall of 2,360 mm (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Monthly rainfall distribution at Ca Mau station during the period of 1990-2022

2.2 Data collection and approach methods

To investigate the impact of heavy rainfall events on flooding in Ca Mau province, the study collected a comprehensive dataset of rainfall and flooding events from 1990 to 2022. The data was obtained from Ca Mau Hydrometeorological Station, which provided valuable insights into the province's rainfall patterns. The analysis revealed that the average annual rainfall in the province is approximately 2394 mm, with a significant concentration of rainfall during the rainy season, which spans from May to November (Figure 2). This period accounts for about 90% of the total annual rainfall, making it a critical time for flooding events. Notably, the months of May and November are the most prone to flooding, due to the combination of heavy rainfall and high tides. The province's low elevation and coastal location make it particularly vulnerable to flooding (Figure 3), especially during the rainy season, which is exacerbated by the impacts of global climate change in recent years.

Figure 3: a) Heavy rainfall event combined with high tides caused local flooding of more than 349 houses in Ca Mau province (Source: Communist Party of Vietnam Electronic News) and b) over 16,000 hectares of rice in Tran Van Thoi district (Ca Mau) were flooded due to high tides combined with prolonged heavy rainfall (Source: Vietnam Law News).

This study employed trend and frequency-duration and intensity analysis to investigate the impact of heavy rainfall events and their return periods on flooding in Ca Mau province. The procedure involved several key steps. First, the daily data series collected rainfall data from Ca Mau station for the period of 1990-2022. The input rainfall data evaluated its quality using Bettitt, SNHT, Buishand and von Neumann tests at 99% confidence levels with the null hypothesis (H0) of homogeneity and alternative hypothesis (Ha) of non-homogeneity.

To analyze the short-duration rainfall, we converted the daily rainfall data into hours durations, including 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, and 8 hours, using a formula (1).

$$R_t = R_{24} \sqrt[3]{\frac{t}{24}} \tag{1}$$

where, R_t is the rainfall depth in mm at t-hr duration, R_{24} is the daily rainfall in mm and t is the duration of rainfall

This allowed us to evaluate the rainfall intensity-duration-frequency (IDF) curves, which are crucial for understanding the relationship between rainfall intensity, duration, and frequency.

The process of establishing IDF curves involved three key steps. First, we fitted the rainfall data series to a cumulative distribution function (CDF) to determine the rainfall intervals. Next, we related the maximum rainfall intensity for each interval to the return periods using the CDF. Finally, we evaluated the cumulative frequency and duration, and the maximum rainfall intensity using the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution, Gumbel function, and Pearson Type III function. The cumulative distribution function $F(x)$ was calculated using a specific formula (2).

$$F(x) = \exp \left[- \left(1 + k \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \right)^{-\frac{1}{k}} \right] \tag{2}$$

where μ , σ , and ξ in the formular (2) are defined as the location, scale, and shape parameter and the location parameter (μ) in the formular (2) was calculated by formular (3):

$$\mu(t) = \mu_1 t + \mu_0 \tag{3}$$

In formular (3) t is time and μ_1 , μ_0 are the intercept and the slope parameters.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Quality assessment of rainfall data

The quality assessment of the rainfall data series at Ca Mau station for the period 1990-2022 is presented in Table 1. The Pettitt test was used to detect any significant deviations in the data series. The test statistic K and the corresponding p -value for the September data series were 83 and 0.834, respectively, indicating that the data series is homogeneous. The SNHT, Buishand and von Neumann tests were also employed to evaluate the homogeneity of the data series. The values of the SNHT, Buishand and von Neumann tests ($T0 = 2.979$ and $p = 0.605$), ($Q = 4.936$ and $p = 0.322$), and ($N = 1.977$ and $p = 0.471$), respectively, indicating that the rainfall data series in September are homogeneous. Similarly, for rainfall in October, the values of the SNHT, Buishand and von Neumann tests were 98 and 0.694, 3.580 and 0.480, 5.165 and 0.267, and 2.158 and 0.667, respectively, suggesting that the rainfall data series in October is also homogeneous.

Table 1: Quality assessment results of September and October rainfall data series at Ca Mau station for the period 1990-2022

Tests	Pettitt		SNHT		Buishand		von Neumann	
	K	p	T0	p	Q	p	N	p
September	83	0.834	2.979	0.605	4.936	0.322	1.977	0.471
October	98	0.694	3.580	0.480	5.165	0.267	2.158	0.667

3.2 Changed trends of rainfall features

Table 2 presents the results of the Mann-Kendall test, Sen's slope estimator, and Durbin-Watson test for detecting trends of rainfall in September and October at Ca Mau station during the period 1990-2022. For rainfall in September, the Mann-Kendall test is 0.177, with a p -value of 0.160. This indicates that the trend in September rainfall is not statistically significant, as the p -value is greater than 0.05. The Sen's slope estimator shows an increase of 3.383 mm per year, suggesting that there may be a slight upward trend in September rainfall (Figure 4). The Durbin-Watson test statistic is 0.192, with a p -value of less than 0.0001. This indicates that the trend in September rainfall is not random, and there is a significant autocorrelation present.

Table 2: Analyzed results of changed trends of rainfall in September and October at Ca Mau station for the period 1990-2022

Variables	Man-Kendall test			Durbin-Watson test		
	Kendall's tau	p	Sen's slope	DW	p	rho
September	0.177	0.160	3.383	0.192	<0,0001	-0.009
October	-0.109	0.394	-2.844	0.349	<0,0001	-0.082

Similarly, rainfall in October also recorded the values of Mann-Kendall test is -0.109 ($p = 0.394$). This indicates that the trend in October rainfall is also not statistically significant, as the p -value is greater than 0.05. The Sen's slope estimator shows a decrease of -2.844 mm per year, suggesting that there may be a slight downward trend in October rainfall (Figure 4). The Durbin-Watson test statistic is 0.349, with a p -value of less than 0.0001. This indicates that the trend in October rainfall is a significant autocorrelation present.

Figure 4: Changed trends of rainfall in September and October at Ca Mau station during the period 1990-2022

3.3 Return intervals of heavy rainfall events

Table 3 presents the results of the analysis of rainfall intensities for different return intervals (e.g., 5, 10, and 20-year) corresponding to durations of 60 minutes, 120 minutes, 180 minutes, and 240 minutes. This analysis is to investigate the rainfall intensities corresponding to various return periods, which are essential for limiting the flood risks and further planning water resources management. For the return interval of 5-year, the results show that the rainfall intensity for a 60-minute duration is 47.2 mm, while for 120 minutes, 180 minutes, and 240 minutes, the intensities are 30.4 mm, 24.7 mm, and 19.6 mm, respectively. For the return interval of 10 years, the rainfall intensities for each duration are 54.9 mm, 35.6 mm, 27.8 mm, and 21.5 mm, respectively. For the return interval of 20 years, the rainfall intensities for each duration are 59.9 mm, 38.7 mm, 29.8 mm, and 23.3 mm, respectively.

Table 3: Simulated results of rainfall intensities for different return intervals

Duration (Minutes)	Return intervals (year)		
	5	10	20
60	47.2	54.9	59.9
120	30.4	35.6	38.7
180	24.7	27.8	29.8
240	19.6	21.5	25.3

A similar study on extreme rainfall events caused the flood in the Ca Mau coastal area under the impacts of climate change by Dang (2020) [7] revealed that the durations from 2 to hours, the rainfall intensities ranged from 25.5 to 37.2 mm/h, respectively, at the 20-year return interval. In overall, the simulation of rainfall intensities for different return intervals reveals that the rainfall intensities increase as the return interval decreases. The results show that the rainfall intensity for a 60-minute duration is higher than for longer durations, while the rainfall intensity for a 240-minute duration is lower than for shorter durations (Figure 5). These findings will be useful for designing and planning water resources management systems, such as dams, reservoirs, and irrigation systems.

Figure 5: Simulated results of rainfall intensities for different return intervals (e.g., 5, 10 and 20-year) corresponding to durations of 60, 120, 180, and 204 minutes at Ca Mau station

4. Conclusion

This study investigated the potential risks of flooding in Ca Mau Province in the context of climate change and sea level rise. The study analyzed rainfall data series from 1990 to 2022 and revealed a significant increase in rainfall intensity and frequency, particularly during the rainy season months. The study also found that the province's low elevation and coastal location make it highly vulnerable to flooding. The results of the intensity-duration-frequency (IDF) curve analysis showed that the rainfall intensity increases as the return period decreases, indicating a higher risk of flooding in the short-term. Furthermore, the analysis of the return intervals of heavy rainfall events revealed that the durations from 2 to 24 hours, the rainfall intensities ranged from 25.5 to 37.2 mm/h, respectively, at the 20-year return interval. These findings have important implications for flood risk management and adaptation strategies in Ca Mau Province, and highlight the need for further research and development of effective flood mitigation measures to protect the province from the impacts of climate change and sea level rise.

References

1. Al-Baldawi THK, Alzuabidi ZZA. (2016), Extreme value analysis of maximum rainfall data in Baghdad city, *Mathematics and Statistics Journal*, 2(3), 1-8.
2. Al-Saji, M., O'Sullivan, J.J, O'Connor, A. (2015). Design impact and significance of non-stationarity of variance in extreme rainfall. *Proc. IAHS* 371, 117–123.
3. Atreya, A., Ferreira, S. (2013). Kriesel Forgetting the flood? An analysis of the flood risk discount over time *Land Econ.*, 89 (4), pp. 577-596.
4. Barbara, N., Athanasios T. Vafeidis, Juliane, Z.M, Robert, J.N., Lalit, K. (2015). Future coastal population growth and exposure to sea-level rise and coastal flooding-a global assessment. *PLoS ONE*, 10 (3), p. e0118571.
5. Berman, M., Baztan, J., Kofinas, G., Vanderlinden, J.P., Chouinard, O., Huctin, J.M., Thomson, K. (2020). Adaptation to climate change in coastal communities: findings from seven sites on four continents *Climatic Change*, 159 (1), pp. 1-16.
6. Botzen, W.J.W., Aerts, J.C.J.H., Van, D.B. (2009). Dependence of flood risk perceptions on socioeconomic and objective risk factors *Water Resources Research*, 45 (10).
7. Dang, T.A. (2020), "Simulating rainfall IDF curve for flood warnings in the Ca Mau coastal area under the impacts of climate change", *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, Vol. 12 No. 5, pp. 705-715.
8. Deb P, Tran DA, Udmale PD. (2015). Assessment of the impacts of climate change and brackish irrigation water on rice productivity and evaluation of adaptation measures in Ca Mau province, Vietnam, *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 121 (1-2).
9. Franz, F., Georgia, W.M. (2021). Pricing climate risk: Are flooding and sea level rise risk capitalised in Australian residential property?, *Climate Risk Management*, 34, 100361.
10. Fu, X., Song, J., Sun, B., Pen, Z. (2016). Living on the edge: estimating the economic cost of sea level rise on coastal real estate in the Tampa Bay region, *Florida Ocean Coast. Manage.*, 133, pp. 11-17.
11. Ghanmi, H., Bargaoui, Z., Mallet, C. (2016). Estimation of intensity-duration-frequency relationships according to the property of scale invariance and regionalization analysis in a Mediterranean coastal area. *Journal of Hydrology*, 541, 38-49.
12. Gordon, M., Deborah, B., Bridget, A. (2007). The rising tide: assessing the risks of climate change and human settlements in low elevation coastal zones *Environ. Urbaniz.*, 19 (1), pp. 17-37.
13. Lint, B., Jacob, F. (2019). Housing investment, sea level rise, and climate change beliefs *Econ. Lett.*, 177, pp. 105-108.
14. Logah, F.Y, Kankam, Y.K, Bekoe, E.O. (2013). Developing short duration rainfall intensity frequency curves for Accra in Ghana. *Inter. J. Lat. Res. Eng. Comp.* 1 (1), 67–73.
15. McInnes, K., Church, J., Monselesan, D., Hunter, J.R., O'Grady, J.G., Haigh, I.D., Zhang, X. (2015). Information for australian impact and adaption planning in response to sea-level rise *Aust. Meteorol. Oceanogr. J.*, 65 (1), pp. 127-149.
16. MNRE- Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment. (2016). Climate change scenarios and sea level rise for Vietnam. Publisher's resources, environment and map of Vietnam.
17. Patrick, W., Charles, G., Dennis, G., Heather, K.A. (2019). Sea level rise, and property prices in the Chesapeake Bay watershed *Land Econ.*, 95 (1), pp. 19-34.
18. Qin, H., et al. (2013). The effects of low impact development on urban flooding under different rainfall characteristics *J. Environ. Manag.*
19. Vu, D.T, Yamada, T., Ishidaira, H. (2018). Assessing the impact of sea level rise due to climate change on seawater intrusion in Mekong Delta, Vietnam. *Water Science & Technology*. Doi: 10.2166/wst.2018.038
20. Wang, J., et al. (2017). Effects of sea level rise, land subsidence, bathymetric change and typhoon tracks on storm flooding in the coastal areas of Shanghai. *Science of The Total Environment*. 621(15), pp. 228-234.